

Preprint

Medical therapy, radiofrequency ablation or cryoballoon ablation as first-line treatment for paroxysmal atrial fibrillation: interpreting efficacy through restricted mean survival time and network meta-analysis

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Abstract

Background: When multiple treatments are available, network meta-analysis can synthesise evidence and rank relative effectiveness. We applied this approach to first-line treatments for paroxysmal atrial fibrillation (medical therapy, radiofrequency ablation or cryoballoon ablation). Individual trials were analysed based on the restricted mean survival time (RMST).

Methods: Data Sources included PubMed and websites of regulatory agencies. Randomised controlled trials assessing first-line treatments for paroxysmal atrial fibrillation were selected. The end-point for our analysis was atrial fibrillation recurrence-free survival at 12 months. At least 2 reviewers abstracted study data and outcomes. Treatments examined for their relative effectiveness included medical therapy, radiofrequency ablation or cryoballoon ablation. Individual trials were examined based on restricted mean survival time (RMST). A Bayesian network meta-analysis was conducted to comparatively evaluate these treatments.

Results: Five trials were included in the analysis: two compared radiofrequency with medical treatment and three cryoballoon with medical treatment. The indirect comparison of radiofrequency ablation vs cryoballoon ablation was assessed in the absence of RCTs. Differences in RMST (with 95% credible intervals) were estimated for all binary comparisons (direct or indirect). Radiofrequency and cryoballoon showed higher effectiveness compared with medical treatment, both at significant levels. In the indirect comparison, radiofrequency showed a numerical advantage over cryoballoon, that however remained far from significance. Ranking in effectiveness was as follows: 1) radiofrequency; 2) cryoballoon; 3) medical treatment.

Conclusions: We generated an updated synthesis of these treatment effectiveness and we ranked them according to a Bayesian probabilistic model.

This preprint presents additional information that integrates the content of our article.

The following material is reported:

- 1) Figure S1: PRISMA flow chart.
- 2) Table S1: Values of RMST estimated from individual trials.
- 3) Figure S2: Values of RMST estimated from individual trials.
- 4) Additional references.

Figure S1. PRISMA flow diagram of our literature search.

Table S1. Characteristics of the 10 cohorts and values of RMST estimated from the time-to-event curves (analysis with milestone of 12 mos)

Data-set	Cohort	t* (mos)	No. of patients	RMST (mos) with 95% confidence interval	Trial-specific gain from 0 to 12 months (mos)	MLS (mos) with 95% confidence interval	Trial-specific lifetime gain (mos)
Andrade et al. 2021	Cryoballoon	12	154	9.36 (8.83 to 9.9)	2.27	20.72 (16.28 to 26.37)	10.8
	Medical therapy		149	7.09 (6.47 to 7.72)		9.92 (8.62 to 11.43)	
Wazni et al. 2021	Cryoballoon	12	104	10.33 (9.66 to 10.99)	1.64	33.71 (18.07 to 62.85)	22.07
	Medical therapy		99	8.69 (7.88 to 9.51)		11.64 (9.65 to 14.06)	
Morillo et al. 2014	Radiofrequency	12	66	9.67 (8.89 to 10.44)	1.54	31.15 (21.93 to 44.31)	15.18
	Medical therapy		61	8.13 (7.24 to 9.02)		15.97 (12.16 to 20.98)	
Wazni et al. 2005	Radiofrequency	12	33	10.98 (10.03 to 11.93)	3.71	not computable†	not computable†
	Medical therapy		37	7.27 (5.99 to 8.54)		not computable†	
Kuniss et al. 2021 [8]	Cryoballoon	12	107	11.16 (10.71 to 11.61)	1.00	44.20 (20.22 to 96.61)	26.37
	Medical therapy	12	111	10.16 (9.58 to 10.75)		17.83 (14.07 to 22.60)	

†The fit based on Weibull function performed under R-platform failed because of insufficient information in the Kaplan-Meier curve.

Abbreviations: t*, milestone; mos, months; RMST, restricted mean survival time; mos, months; MLS, mean lifetime survival (estimated through Weibull extrapolation).

Figure S2. Graphical presentation of RMST values (in months) estimated from the 10 arms of the 5 trials; vertical bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Abbreviations: cryo., cryoballoon ablation; radio., radiofrequency ablation; med., medical therapy.

Additional references

Topic: restricted mean survival time

-Rahmadian AP, Delos Santos S, Parshad S et al. Quantifying the survival benefits of oncology drugs with a focus on immunotherapy using restricted mean survival time. *J. Natl Compr. Canc. Netw.* 18(3), 278–285 (2020).

Topic: Bayesian network meta-analysis

Messori A, Fadda V, Maratea D, Trippoli S. First-line treatments for chronic lymphocytic leukaemia: interpreting efficacy data by network meta-analysis. *Ann Hematol.* 2015 Jun;94(6):1003-9. doi: 10.1007/s00277-015-2310-6. Epub 2015 Feb 14. PMID: 25677267.

Topic: the “simplified figure” for reporting network meta-analysis results

-Fadda V, Maratea D, Trippoli S, Messori A. Network meta-analysis. Results can be summarised in a simple figure. *BMJ.* 2011 Mar 23;342:d1555. doi:10.1136/bmj.d1555.

- De Vecchis R, Ariano C, Rigopoulos A, Noutsias M. Graphical representation of network meta-analysis: an iconographic support to the complexity of multiple data comparisons. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2019 Jan;75(1):131-132. doi: 10.1007/s00228-018-2551-0. Epub 2018 Sep 10. PMID: 30203129.

Topic: previous network meta-analyses based on restricted mean survival time

-Petit C, Blanchard P, Pignon JP, Lueza B. Individual patient data network meta-analysis using either restricted mean survival time difference or hazard ratios: is there a difference? A case study on locoregionally advanced nasopharyngeal carcinomas. *Syst Rev.* 2019 Apr 15;8(1):96. doi: 10.1186/s13643-019-0984-x. PMID: 30987679; PMCID: PMC6463649.

Topic: errors in published trials that we found when reconstructing patient-level data and consequent corrections

-Bartoli L, Ferracane E, Trippoli S, Messori A. Recurrence-free survival curve in the RAAFT2 trial evaluating catheter ablation vs medical therapy as first line in paroxysmal atrial fibrillation: a re-analysis (preprint). Open Science Framework, published 8 April 2021, available at <https://osf.io/c2qst/>

-Bartoli L, Ferracane E, Trippoli S, Messori A. Evaluating catheter ablation vs medical therapy as first line in paroxysmal atrial fibrillation: outcomes of the RAAFT2 trial. *Circulation: Arrhythmia and Electrophysiology* (online only), published 26 March 2021, access - through the “Discuss” option- at <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/CIRCEP.119.007414>

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